

8T – Majestic Bosons

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Abstract:

By analyzing the primordial coupling constants equation, author will present an expansion of the particle wave duality – using the spin form. In particular, the author argues that because of the spin increments of one-half exactly, there exist a Bosonic class which behave according to the Fermi rules. Those Bosons have higher chance to be created as alignment of composite Bosons, which are prime and independent themselves. Those Bosons due to their composite alignment require extra Quanta of energy.

Introduction

The main pillars of the 8T can be classified as part of two subclasses. The first subclass is curvature diverging, isomorphic to prime numbers, an idea which yielded the primordial coupling series. The series takes the form which is invariant to all coupling terms, i.e. $8 + (1)$ for the first and $8 \times (\mathcal{P}_n) + (K)$ for the higher coupling terms, in which the parameter (K) is composed of invariant three and the max prime in a prime sequence, (\mathcal{P}_n) , under a real range. That is $(K) = 3 + (\mathcal{P}_n)$.

$$\left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_{V\mu} + (e^-)_{\mu} \right) + N_{V\mu} = 30, 128, 850, 9254 \dots$$

The theory is also considering the mass sequence to be of the form $8 - (1)$ given by a decrease pattern of all masses given by the ratio aspiring zero. The subject matter in hand is the following question: what is the implications of the spin form concerning the classes of particles. In the 8T, there exist the following classification:

Spin 0: $2N_0$ variations

Spin $\frac{1}{2}$: $2N_0 + 3$ variations

Spin 1: $2N_0 + 3 + N_V$ variations

Spin N = $2N_0 + 3 + N_{V1} + N_{V2} \dots$ variations

For the sake of this idea, it is possible to expend and specify the last category as the following:

Spin 0: $2N_0$ variations

Spin $\frac{1}{2}$: $2N_0 + 3$ variations

Spin 1: $2N_0 + 3 + N_V$ variations

Spin $\frac{3}{2}$: $2N_0 + 3 + N_{V1} + N_{V2} \dots$ variations

Spin 2 = $2N_0 + 3 + N_{V1} + N_{V2} + N_{V3}$ variations

It does not have to be three Bosons for the spin two category, two lepton emitting together is valid option as well. The key point to take is the following. According to the primordial in spin form, there exist a class of Bosons with Fermionic spin. The author used that fact to express the particle wave-duality which is the result of spin variation of the system due to measurement. However it was not emphasized at the time, the coupling term than of the Lepton and the Bosons can be considered a decay of this Bosonic particles, let \mathcal{M} stand for "Majestic" .

$$\mathcal{M}_{Bose} \leftrightarrow (e^-)_{\mu} + N_{(V)k1\mu} + N_{(V)k2\mu}$$

$$\mathcal{M}_{Bose} \leftrightarrow (e^-)_{\mu} + (e^-)_{\mu} + N_{(V)K\mu}$$

Since the Electron is isomorphic to the Boson of the weak interaction, it is possible to represent as the following:

$$\mathcal{M}_{Bose} \rightarrow (W^-)_{\mu} + (W^-)_{\mu} + N_{(V)K\mu}$$

$$(e^-)_{\mu} \equiv (W^-)_{\mu} \equiv 3$$

The isomorphism is given by the coupling second term. It is supported by the fact that both carry the same charge. This new class of Bosons will present a behavior typical of Fermions, that is they may repel each other, not present a wave-like motion such as their lower class Bosons of spin one, but rather "particle like" behavior, they will obey Fermi rules. Since at each class of Bosons, additional terms are needed, the chance of creating the alignment is aspiring zero, so according to that, the stability of those Bosons, which are composite, is aspiring zero, and can be considered short ranged. The same arguments used on the Graviton compositions. The interesting thing is, that despite this short lifetime, the chance of observation will increase at high-energy particle collisions, as the collision creates the condition of alignment of Bosons, which needed extra amount of quanta as they contain more terms. So perfect alignment of Bosons in spatial and temporal, will lead to their alignment in such way that higher spin forms will present themselves and then decay to their composite Bosons. In contrast to the particle wave duality idea which emphasized only the total spin of the system, and referred only to the observed particle varying Quanta and spin due to another Boson which was inserted during measurement, this idea is different as it regard each coupling as a possible decay of a particle. It also different is it allocate an entire class between the classes of spin one particles, and spin two particles. If spin is incremented in half units, there must be additional classes between those integers' particles.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8T – The Grand Theory of Everything" In: (2021)

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